

Mobility-Hub: Next Generation Traffic Light Controller integrated into the Computing Continuum with Serverless Technology and AI-enabled Orchestration

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Abstract—This paper presents *Mobility-Hub* (M-Hub), a next-generation *Traffic Light Controller* (TLC) developed by ACISA that leverages the power of cloud-edge continuum computing, *Digital Twins* (DT), 5G, and *Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything* (C-V2X) technology to transform traffic management into a dynamic and intelligent system - ready for the incoming *Cooperative, Intelligent Transport* (C-ITS) services being deployed in many cities to improve safety and optimize traffic management.

M-Hub acts as an open-far-edge computing platform, enabling real-time data processing, third party containerized applications, and decision-making at the network far edge. As part of this process, customised DTs based on data gathered from diverse data sources (such as vehicular data, traffic detectors, smart cameras, environmental data etc.) are used to generate traffic simulations in available infrastructure. This is enabled through integration with COGNIT - an open-source cloud-edge continuum framework that facilitates the orchestration of distributed and heterogeneous resources and abstracts complexity to end clients.

Through the use of DTs, M-Hub can dynamically adjust traffic signal timings, optimize traffic flow, and reduce congestion with the optimal use of available computational resources. M-Hub has the potential to revolutionize urban mobility, enhancing safety, improving efficiency, and reducing environmental impact.

Keywords— Cloud-Edge Continuum; Digital Twin; 5G; C-V2X; AI; Urban Mobility; Intelligent Transport Systems, Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM).

I. Introduction

Increasing urbanization and growing demand for mobility have placed significant pressure on existing traffic management systems, where urban mobility is facing unprecedented challenges due to increasing traffic volumes, expanding urban areas, and the rise of autonomous vehicles and smart cities. Traditional TLC (often based on static and fixed signal timings and outdated technology) are limited in their capabilities, and struggle

to keep pace with the changes and the complexities of modern urban environments. In urban environments, many ITS sub-systems (e.g., traffic light controllers, smart cameras, inductive loop detectors, Bluetooth sensors, etc.) must co-exist to monitor and control traffic in situations of high complexity. Nowadays, the emergence of new sources of vehicular data and networks through Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication technologies reactivates the need for new solutions, as most existing systems cannot address the *Quality of Service* (QoS) requirements of traffic demands or low latency edge processing. These problems are addressed by ACISA's M-Hub[1] and its Mobility Platform, Saturno [3].

V2X networks consisting of *Vehicle-to-vehicle* (V2V), *Vehicle-to-pedestrian* (V2P), *Vehicle-to-Infrastructure* (V2I), and *Vehicle-to-Network* (V2N) communication are envisioned as a fundamental enabler for ITS, where vehicles are equipped with an *On-Board Unit* (OBU), which includes a V2X communication stack and allows on-board sensor data to interact with neighbouring vehicles, *Road Side Units* (RSUs), and cloud applications over cellular connectivity [4, 5]. V2X connectivity enables vehicles to perceive beyond their onboard sensors, and enables *Connected Cooperative and Automated Mobility* services (CCAM) – which are intended to improve traffic efficiency and road safety for ITS.

To improve transportation efficiency, safety, and comfort on the road, V2X services have multiple and complex application scenarios, ranging from enhancing real-time safety and efficiency on the road to autonomous driving. Moreover, it is believed that as the number of autonomous cars increases significantly due to urbanization and technological progress, there will be massive usage of V2X communications that promote the development of intelligent autonomous vehicles. This increasing demand poses new communication issues in V2X networks [6 - 8].

As a result of these developments, existing 5G networks will face significant capacity limitations, resulting in new scientific and technical challenges for V2X communication networks in terms of data rate, latency, coverage, intelligence level, network connectivity, vulnerabilities and security issues [9]. To help smart-city service providers manage such complexity and deploy faster to meet the QoS requirements of different services, platforms need to be interoperable, and support applications that could be deployed either in Edge, Cloud, or On-Premises that can be managed remotely using Cloud-native practices.

Cloud computing infrastructures have evolved from centralised data centres to distributed federations of processing and storage resources – often known as the “Computing Continuum”. The continuum offers many opportunities for next-generation smart transport systems, including lower network latencies, better scalability, and smart offloading of computation on resource-constrained devices – but at the cost of greatly increased complexity in development, deployment, and management. Besides infrastructure complexity, many intersections in a big city are equipped with a variety of information systems from different providers that add context information to the traffic operators, and eventually to road users. We are modelling city intersections and creating DTs with the data provided by all those systems, to present a unified interface to traffic operators in the *Control Center* (CC), and to make it possible to develop predictive traffic models and simulations to increase safety, reduce emissions and facilitate interaction with users and DTs in other intersections.

This paper presents its solution utilising the COGNIT a framework [2], a 6M Euro project funded by the EU Horizon Europe program. COGNIT aims to build an open-source software stack to enable the deployment of *Function-as-a-Service* (FaaS) technology in the Cloud Continuum, with the aim of utilising artificial intelligence techniques to optimally orchestrate available computing resources. The project consortium is composed of 10 organisations from 6 different member states across Europe.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces how ACISA address the challenges encountered by city traffic operators dealing with multiple providers, applications, and subsystems, through the establishment of an open edge-cloud infrastructure. The objectives of this approach are presented in Section III, followed by an explanation of the methodology in Section IV. Section V concludes the paper.

II. Contribution

Historically, traffic management in most cities has been carried out by creating a *Traffic Light Controller* (TLC) program for each intersection, to optimize some traffic parameters synchronized with other TLCs. This is done in a static and centralized way and is not changed unless the layout of the intersection changes significantly. ACISA and other technology providers have been developing public bus priority systems for many years, initially relying on costly *Commercial Off-The-Shelf* (COTS) radio transceivers and later transitioning to more cost-effective 3G/4G equipment as it became affordable for embedded systems. In both cases, the equipment and communication protocol were proprietary, so solutions from different providers could not coexist in the same city. The former approach was an expensive and tailor-made solution, where the priority decision was computed locally: every TLC was attached to a radio transceiver and a gateway that translated the priority request to a dry contact pulse. The information needed by each gateway (*e.g.* Bus ID, Line ID, distance to detection points, etc.) was loaded one by one. This cannot scale and is difficult to maintain.

The 3G/4G approach improved the operation process because thanks to the ubiquitous cellular communication, they can be accessed from the CC, greatly improving configuration and maintenance tasks. In this solution, everything is managed centrally from the CC, with all TLCs and on-board gateways connected to the software solution used for traffic management. This approach is more scalable compared to the former, but introduces higher latency (*i.e.*, TLC and gateways must be connected to the CC via RS-485, fiber-optic or 3G/4G networks), higher programming complexity, and decreased availability (normally due to network issues).

Over the last decades, new technologies have been incorporated into intersections to enrich context knowledge (intelligent cameras, Bluetooth and wireless sensors, V2X RSUs, pollution and noise sensors, dynamic information panels, *Vulnerable Road Users* (VRU) detection, etc.) which complicate the work of operators in the traffic control center even further; indeed, a plethora of applications from different providers coexist in a non-integrated fashion.

To address the challenges mentioned above, we propose our advanced TLC, named *Mobility-Hub* (M-Hub), which is designed to bring together core functional elements of edge platforms for smart mobility solutions, through containerized and intelligent applications developed and implemented in M-Hub which allows supporting complex or simple services with different QoS requirements to be managed either in edge

(i.e., M-Hub) or in Cloud within unified interfaces and data formats. The key features of M-Hub are: i) to virtualize, communicate and deploy advanced computing services and applications, and to make them available to cities and other service providers, ii) to act as a local gateway and secured communication Hub for all the information subsystems deployed at an intersection, iii) an infrastructure able to host critical services that require low latency, high bandwidth and local communication with other subsystems (such as CCAM applications or safety applications based on intelligent video processing).

M-Hub acts as an open edge platform and communication gateway to other subsystems installed at an intersection by different providers, and besides applications developed by ACISA, also offers the possibility to third parties to develop applications that may integrate with the different subsystems in the intersection to enrich its own data and algorithms, by means of data contract agreements. M-Hub provides local data processing i.e., data quality assessment, missing data detection, time series inference predictive models or data protocol transformation to comply with a particular standard.

M-Hubs are normally connected to SATURNO, an UNE 178104:2017 compliant Smart Mobility platform, built as a cloud-native *Software as a Service* (SaaS) solution. SATURNO is a modular open suite with a powerful web *User Interface* (UI) and RESTful *Application Programming Interface* (API), that includes solutions to address different mobility domains, such as (inter)urban traffic management, low emissions zones

Figure 1 – Classic ACISA’s 3-Tier mobility management architecture

(LEZ), access control to cities, environmental monitoring, fleet management, administrative back-office integration, etc. For those use cases requiring low latency and high availability, and additional computational power than that offered by a traditional TLC, we use a 3-tier infrastructure (as shown in Fig. 1), where additional computing resources are allocated in the Edge (CC of the city), and in the very far Edge (M-Hub), as shown in Fig.1.

Depending on the latency demand, storage needs or legal agreements, SATURNO services may be deployed either in a public or private cloud, on city council premises or in a hybrid deployment. To facilitate the management of all those distributed resources, we are participating in the COGNIT project to incorporate the serverless framework as part of our infrastructure. This framework efficiently manages those distributed resources as a continuum infrastructure. Its serverless paradigm approach not only simplifies the setup and maintenance operations but also significantly reduces operational costs.

Continuum infrastructures are highly complex and dynamic; they must process a wide variety of ever-changing software workloads (which may have different and dynamically changing requirements and service-level agreements) across geographically dispersed nodes (as shown in Fig. 2). Each node within the system can be heterogeneous, with different types of hardware, pricing, energy sources, etc. The management of such systems is a huge challenge; as the dynamicity and complexity are too much for human control, *autonomous resource management mechanisms* become essential.

At the heart of COGNIT, application developers and device clients submit functions to a Provisioning Engine, which provides a Serverless runtime for the function. The Provisioning Engine then interacts with a Cloud-Edge manager, which has the goal of placing the runtime on an appropriate node within the Continuum. To do this, an AI-enabled orchestrator component is placed.

The orchestrator provides “intelligence” to the system, and consists of a library of different predictive models that are trained based on system and application requirements, to provide optimal placement to fulfil the objectives of both functions and infrastructure – for example, the system may aim to place serverless runtimes on nodes with the highest energy efficiency possible (for example – using renewable power sources or using efficient processing hardware) whilst still maintaining the service-level requirements (e.g. latency, price, etc.) of the function itself.

Figure 2 – The COGNIT Computing Continuum architecture.

III. Objectives

The main objectives of the solution proposed are i) to demonstrate the benefits of using a cloud-edge continuum architecture described in Sec. II, to develop more secure, available, lower latency smart mobility services, to ii) support an innovative new serverless paradigm for edge application management and enhanced digital sovereignty for users and developers; iii) to enable on-demand high available & low latency deployment of applications using on-premises city infrastructure (increasing resource utilization); iv) to optimize data placement according to changes in energy efficiency heuristics and application demands and behaviour; v) to enable secure and trusted execution of the serverless runtimes that support the new V2X services that ACISA have installed in real environments; vi) to achieve a faster pace of innovation, more resilient systems and less

proprietary technologies; and vii) to align with the CCAM objective to create a more user-centred and inclusive mobility system, increasing road safety while reducing congestion and environmental footprint.

Using the cloud-edge infrastructure described in Sec. II, we aim to leverage open technologies in the cloud and edge computing fields that will benefit our customers by attracting the vibrant open-source community to the ITS domain. To this aim, we leverage the privileged location held by each TLC in the layout of a city to provision an enhanced distributed computing capacity, which enables real low-latency high-capacity infrastructure to deploy advanced services for traffic management. Given that the infrastructure as a whole is ultimately owned by city councils, providing such open, standard-based infrastructure will allow cities to deploy robust smart-city IoT & mobility services relying on its already deployed traffic infrastructure.

IV. Methodology

We utilize the benefits of COGNIT Serverless services to automate resource provisioning across the continuum based on edge applications' requirements. In this paper, we aim to present how M-Hub enables low latency Infrastructure to Vehicle (I2V) services – based on ETSI and 3GPP standards – such as Public Transport Priority (PTP), Time-To-Green information (TTG) and GLOSA (Green Light Optimal Speed Advisory) as harmonized in the C-ROADS platform.

ETSI defines cooperative V2X communication technology under the acronym C-ITS-G5, or Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems, originally based on Dedicated Short Range Communications (DSRC), and documented under various European Norms (EN) and Technical Specifications (TS) published by ETSI. 3GPP also included V2X functionalities starting from LTE version 14, based on cellular radio technology (LTE, 5G, 6G). In January 2020, ETSI, in collaboration with 5GAA, published EN 303 613 [10], which defines the use of C-V2X as the access layer technology for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) in the 5 GHz frequency band. This ensures that all standards-compliant providers will be interoperable, avoiding vendor lock-in.

Vehicle priority on intelligent intersections is standardized in UNE-CEN ISO/TS 19091, and falls under the Signalised Intersections (SI) service, having been included in C-ROADS in 2019. To integrate these new technologies into the traffic management of a city, additional requirements such as more edge computing power and lower latency are needed, which are achieved with ACISA's M-Hub. The priority request functionality described above conforms to the principles established in UNE-CEN ISO/TS 19091. This standard is based on ETSI and SAE specifications.

Within the first project use case, we will implement SI-TLP and SI-EVP through the selection of different prioritization levels, with the help of intersection's Digital Twin. Devices using V2X communications (RSU and OBU) will utilize digital signature mechanisms based on certificates issued by the national PKI deployed by CTAG for Spain and Portugal. The established security model follows a common European trust model and is based on the European Certification Policy for C-ITS, which references relevant ETSI standards for certificates and PKI management as the underlying technical basis. These provisions are valid for all services, use cases, and harmonized scenarios within C-Roads. For efficiency, complete messages are not encrypted but are digitally signed, ensuring both integrity and authenticity of the sender. To prevent key hijacking, certificates have a validity period and must be renewed periodically.

Both Saturno suite and the Mobility-Hub have been defined and created in accordance with the ISO 27001 standard, thus ensuring a robust information security management system. This certification ensures that rigorous controls have been implemented to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information throughout the systems' lifecycle, as well as the creation of risk mitigation plans related to information security, compliance with legal and regulatory requirements (e.g., GDPR), and continuous improvement of security processes.

These services aim to enhance the driving experience by providing speed advice, traffic light information and countdowns or green priority, to reduce energy consumption and minimize stops, promoting eco-friendlier and energy-efficient driving. They rely on standardized messages such as Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM), Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENM) and In-Vehicle Information Messages (IVIM) in accordance with the standard ETSI TS 103 301.

The COGNIT continuum infrastructure allows to provision of additional resources to help those services, like supporting the deployment of a DT at every intersection, with the possibility to run on-demand simulations to predict the intensity and occupation of the road.

In particular, PTP as an important mobility service allows public transport to receive priority over other vehicles when approaching an intersection by modifying, when necessary, TLC phase timings, either by extending the green phase, reducing the red one or even forcing a new phase (in the case of emergency vehicles). The precise and detailed information that can be obtained with the aim of V2X systems, and the additional computational power at the intersection provided by the M-Hub, allow us to be more precise and consider additional information before granting priority, such as traffic intensity and occupation, incidents, traffic jam, near bus stop, weather conditions or pollution, together with contextual information the public transport might send (*i.e.*, bus location, speed, direction, delay or advance with respect to the schedule, passenger occupancy, etc.)

M-Hub has been designed as an advanced TLC in the far edge, aiming to reduce response times and improve the efficiency of public transportation and emergency services, where it can detect approaching vehicles such as buses or emergency vehicles via V2X technology, and then adjust the traffic signals accordingly to grant priority. M-Hub collects traffic information from the subsystems it connects continuously, to synchronize with the DT of the intersection. Periodically it may also need to perform simulations to evaluate future traffic status and What-If scenarios based on current context data, but this task is off-loaded to the COGNIT framework, which will receive the inputs and requirements to execute a traffic simulation and will set and execute that task within the most optimal resource available (Fig. 3).

The continuum infrastructure is hosted by servers allocated either in the public cloud or at ACISA's private cloud data center; M-Hub Gold servers, usually allocated in the city council infrastructure and with higher computational resources than M-Hub Silver, are installed at city intersections.

Figure 3 – C-V2X based Bus priority use case within a cloud-edge continuum infrastructure.

IV. Public Bus Priority Use Case Description and System Architecture

ACISA deployed a public transport prioritization system based on C-V2X communication technology in Granada, a city in southern Spain. It is based on direct interaction between the C-V2X subsystem and ACISA's M-Hub in the intersections, edge resources at the Center for Comprehensive Mobility Management of Granada (CGIM) and SATURNO, deployed in our private cloud in a 3-tier architecture as shown in Fig. 1&3. In this real scenario running, we deployed a Proof of Concept (PoC) where we used the COGNIT framework to offload simulations of the intersection under test, implementing the architecture shown in Fig. 3, and following the standard UNE-CEN ISO/TS 19091 that defines the use V2X communications for applications related to signalized intersections.

A public bus requests priority to M-Hub by sending a standardized V2X *Signal Request Extended Message* (SREM) once per second, after receiving the intersection's layout and TLC phase information from M-Hub through *Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message* (SPATEM) and *Map Extended Message* (MAPEM), as defined in ETSI TS-103-301. The SREM includes essential details such as the bus ID, Lane ID, and, when available, passenger occupancy level.

M-Hub processes V2X messages, and filters those requesting for traffic light priority. Every time an SREM is received, it first evaluates if it is a valid request, and then, will launch the internal process to locally evaluate the permission. M-Hub will start tracking the bus position by means of the Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM) sent by the vehicle every 100ms, to ensure that buses do not stop unexpectedly due to traffic congestion, bus stops or any other unplanned reason. Once the bus reaches a specified location (particular to each lane of the intersection, at each intersection) the final evaluation takes place: M-Hub evaluates current traffic status based on feedback from the DT, verifies any delay/advance of the bus with respect to the planned

schedule, evaluate the last simulation results, and finally initiates the necessary traffic light phase changes to ensure it will find a green light on time.

Every interaction with the COGNIT framework is done by means of lambda functions executed against the serverless COGNIT infrastructure. Should the M-Hub need extra data from external systems, it will be able to request the missing information with simple lambda functions that abstract the M-Hub from the complexities in the backend; information may come from either SATURNO suite, *Automatic Vehicle Location* (AVL) systems from public transport operator, city council information endpoints, public administrations databases or any other related information system. This abstraction is particularly useful for the M-Hub to become an open platform for third parties. Those external parties should not have access to the internal details of the infrastructure to ensure security and trust, simplicity of development and deployment, decoupling and low-footprint applications.

Up until today, all the necessary information to process traffic priority requests is held in centralized systems like SATURNO, but the aim is to downward these decisions closer to the requestor with the aim of COGNIT serverless framework.

Cloud-edge - Hub continuum evaluation

As explained in Section II, both local-based and CC-based approaches present their own challenges. Increasing the computation power inside the TLC, enables to take local decisions that decrease response time while ensuring service availability. Authors in [19] present a model for efficient multi-player and multi-task computation offloading in VR applications, leveraging mobile edge-cloud computing to ensure optimal network latency and energy consumption. They describe a model similar to the one proposed in this paper, where main computational tasks are shared between user-side VR devices and edge resources (in this case MEC servers instead of the city council's on-premises), and demonstrate a reduction in network latency and energy consumption between 27% and 11% when compared to cloud, edge or user device execution alone, providing enough resources are allocated in the edge to allow user device's task offloading. Authors in [12] also emphasize the need for enough computational resources and inter-network bandwidth at the edge infrastructure to mimic cloud performance and reduce latency.

Our priority system in Granada is deployed on the main line of municipal public transport, composed of 39 intersections connected to the metro network of the city, where each is equipped with an M-Hub and a C-V2X RSU. The minimum computational requirements of the edge node inside the M-Hub is includes and Intel Celeron Quad Core @2 GHz, 8GB DDR3 RAM, and 120 GB SSD SATA storage. There are also 18 public buses with C-V2X OBUs.

Conversely, CGIM is equipped with two dedicated servers tailored for virtualization and mobility management applications, featuring the specified characteristics such us 2 x Intel Xeon-S 12 Core G10 2.4GHz, 8 x DDR4 16GB DDR4 2933 MHz and 7 x 1.8TB 12G SAS 10K 2.5IN 512E HDD

VI. Conclusion

M-Hub represents a significant step forward in the evolution of traffic management. By leveraging cloud-edge computing, DTs, 5G, and C-V2X technology, M-Hub enables a more intelligent, adaptive, and data-driven

approach to mobility management, in particular when the COGNIT FaaS framework is used for important smart city use cases such as public bus priority. M-Hub has the ability, combined with the SATURNO cloud platform, to optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and enhance safety; this has the potential to transform the way we move around our cities. As we move towards a future of smart cities and autonomous vehicles, M-Hub will play a critical role in ensuring the efficient, sustainable, and safe movement of people and goods in our urban environments. The use case presented provides performance information about i) applying V2X technology for public bus and emergency vehicle prioritization, and ii) using a serverless framework to dynamically provision resources to execute heavy or centralized tasks. This combination presents a novelty in the smart city context. In ongoing and future work, the DT of each intersection in Granada's piloted site will be modelled, including data from M-Hub, intersection layout, traffic demand models, V2X services and coverage, public transport schedule, and other external data sources (i.e. 3D models, weather, noise, pollution, etc.) generalizing the methodology to be used at different cities or even interurban scenarios.

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